

CLASSICAL AND MODERN PROBLEMS OF HYDRAULIC SYSTEM DYNAMICS RESEARCH

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Abstract: In the article, the stability of the movement of a hydraulic drive with an open control circuit in the presence of nonlinear damping of the negative resistance type is investigated.

Keywords: Hydraulic drives, TAR, TAC, specific nonlinear systems.

A drive is a device that provides implementation and regulation, including remote, automatic and semi-automatic (i.e., with the participation of a human operator), movements, positions, or efforts of the executive organs of machines.

If a liquid is used as a working fluid, then the drive is called hydraulic. In most cases, an external energy source (tracking or regulated systems) is used.

The hydraulic drive is based on hydraulic mechanisms, i.e., mechanisms in which a working fluid is used as at least one of the links [2].

The paper considers hydraulic drives operating according to the volumetric principle, i.e., drives in whose actuator (hydraulic motor, hydraulic cylinder or turn signal) the working fluid provides geometric connections due to its volume. Therefore, the working fluid should be considered as one of the main elements of the hydraulic drive, the dynamic and static compliance of which determine its dynamic properties, which also depend on the properties of sealing devices, especially when working at high pressures.

On relatively powerful mobile road construction machines and cars, hydraulic steering mechanisms are used (a constant supply pump and a throttle control hydraulic booster or a system with a metering pump); these mechanisms turn out to be structurally complex in some cases due to the need for remote placement of the actuator, which makes it difficult to implement feedback.

The natural tendency to increase pressure has led to the emergence of a new generation of hydraulic system elements with a wider use of new technology and various components of improved quality.

The creation of hydraulic equipment elements that meet modern requirements is associated with the development of new calculation methods that consider dynamic processes and deformations of the working fluid caused by them, changes in its viscosity and many other features of other elements of hydraulic automation [6].

A specific, often occurring type of instability in hydraulic systems is the presence of self-oscillating modes when tracking the control signal. At the same time, the system can be stable in the entire range of possible initial conditions, although it detects significant oscillation [3].

To date, the theory of nonlinear oscillations has been widely developed both in theoretical terms and in practical applications. This was facilitated by the work of A.A. Andronov and his students. The ideas and methods proposed by A.A. Andronov are extremely

fruitful, they are increasingly being used in various fields of science where they deal with oscillatory processes.

In the work of A.A. Andronov "Poincare limit cycles and the theory of self-oscillations", "real mathematics" was first brought to the aid of the theory of self-oscillations, which made it possible to give an accurate definition of the self-oscillations of the system and put the whole question of self-oscillation research on a mathematical basis [4].

The essence of this major discovery made by A.A. Andronov lies in the proposal to interpret the consideration of the motion of a dynamical system in the form of a geometric image – the motion of the depicting point along trajectories in the phase space of the system, and most importantly – in the adequacy of processes with unnamed oscillations in nonlinear and non-conservative systems, called A.A.

Andronov's "self-oscillations", the limit cycle of A. Poincare. The idea expressed by A.A. Andronov: "The limit cycle is a geometric image depicting the periodic motion of the self-oscillating system in phase space; it is a closed curve to which neighboring phase trajectories asymptotically approach."

This discovery also contained a direct indication of the need to use the works of A.M. Lyapunov in solving the issues of stability of limit cycles, since only stable limit cycles correspond to real self-oscillations. Limit cycles can be stable and unstable. A.A. Andronov also showed that the motion displayed by a stable limit cycle has Lyapunov stability, i.e., the deviation of the imaging point on the phase plane from the motion stable by Lyapunov, small enough at the initial moment of time, remains arbitrarily small for any time.

This discovery was the impetus for the development of nonlinear oscillation theory. A strict mathematical definition of self-oscillations was given, their clear physical interpretation in relation to nonlinear autonomous systems of arbitrary nature, and a requirement was put forward for a complete qualitative analysis of the behavior of phase trajectories, i.e., clarification of the complete topological structure of the division of the phase space of the system into trajectories.

"Every idealization "has the ability to avenge itself," has the ability to create internal difficulties."

The idea of rough systems developed by A.A. Andronov together with L.S. Pontryagin [5] is extremely fruitful. Such a system is called rough, the qualitative nature of the movement of which does not change with a sufficiently small change in parameters.

What is the physical justification for the coarseness of the system when writing a differential equation? The researcher never considers and cannot consider all, universally, factors that, one way or another, affect the behavior of systems. On the other hand, none of the factors considered can remain absolutely unchanged during the movement of a dynamic system; therefore, the parameters of a real dynamic system cannot be considered absolutely constant, but only approximately constant.

Meanwhile, often some qualitative features of the idealized scheme under consideration are due to well-known, well-defined qualitative relations, namely some equalities between the parameters describing the scheme of equations, and these qualitative features disappear with an arbitrarily small change in the quantitative relations between the parameters.

Thus, the introduction of the concept of system coarseness sharply distinguishes a certain class of dynamical systems with very characteristic general features of the division of phase space into trajectories.

No less fruitful is the idea that was introduced into the qualitative theory of differential equations by A.A. Andronov, this is the idea of studying the qualitative picture of the division of phase space into trajectories depending on the parameter (bifurcation theory).

It is interesting to change the qualitative picture of the integral curves of the differential equation when changing the parameter included in the equation. With a continuous change in the parameter, the change in the pattern of integral curves does not always occur continuously: at some parameter values, qualitative changes occur, for example, limit cycles appear or disappear, singular points (equilibrium states) merge, etc. Such parameter values are called bifurcation values.

This new approach makes it possible to draw conclusions about given differential equations in which the laws of appearance, disappearance, mutual transformation of singular points, limit cycles and separates can be found when the parameters change.

They allowed A.A. Andronov to give a picture (on a simple example) of two types of evolution of the phase plane of a lamp generator when changing the parameter characterizing feedback—soft" and "hard" occurrence of oscillations.

The introduction into the theory of nonlinear oscillations of the method of point transformations in its modern form, which allows us to study the general provisions of qualitative theory with equal completeness and effectively and accurately solve the problems of studying the dynamics of specific nonlinear systems of arbitrary nature, is the largest scientific result of A.A. Andronov [8].

The method of point transformations is currently an effective tool for the precise study of several classes of nonlinear dynamical systems, elucidation, and proof of many general issues of the theory of nonlinear oscillations, the qualitative theory of nonlinear differential equations, the theory of automatic control and control systems. In numerous cases, it turns qualitative methods into analytical methods for the study of nonlinear dynamical systems, allows us to achieve final concrete results in finding periodic (and stationary) movements, studying their stability and partitioning parameter spaces into areas of various qualitative behavior of the nonlinear dynamical systems under study [8].

Methods of the theory of automatic regulation (TAR) and methods of the theory of automatic control (TAC) have been significantly developed in recent decades and are effective in the research and calculations of dynamic processes occurring in machines, apparatuses, machine tools and other devices [46,60].

Examples of such processes are vibration in machines and machines and other devices, forced fluid fluctuations in pressure paths associated with the cyclical working processes of machines or apparatuses, self-oscillation of individual structural units, etc.

After the invention of steam engines and the advent of factory production, various liquid-powered devices began to be used to transfer energy and control machines. At the beginning of the XX century. High-speed power drives were required to control the machines. These conditions were met by hydraulic drives, in which, in comparison with electric drives, force fields of high intensity were provided in the direction of the transmitted movements[6].

In [1], the stability of the motion of a hydraulic drive with an open control circuit in the presence of nonlinear damping of the negative resistance type was investigated. Using the method, the conditions for the existence of an aperiodic transient process, the conditions for the occurrence of self-oscillations are derived, and a method for changing the drive parameters that provides the desired dynamic properties is established.

In [3], the stability of hydromechanical systems with a control action at the input is investigated and a method of harmonic linearization is proposed using the separation of the characteristic equation of a harmonically linearized system into two components: relatively slowly changing and oscillatory.

When studying the stability of hydraulic systems involving two or more collinearities (for example, the nonlinearity of the regulator, friction in the spool and friction in the load), the method of amplitude trajectories is proposed in [9].

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